

THE ROLE OF JOB SATISFACTION IN MEDIATING THE EFFECTS OF COMPETENCE AND LEADERSHIP STYLE ON TEACHER PERFORMANCE

SUSANTO¹, WILSON BANGUN² and DARWIN LIE³

¹Student of Management Doctoral Program, University of Prima Indonesia.

^{2,3}Lecturer of Management Doctoral Program, University of Prima Indonesia.

Email: ¹Susanto.chang@gmail.com ²wilson.bangun@yahoo.co.id, ³liedarwin5555@gmail.com,

Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine the direct and indirect effects of competence and leadership style on teacher performance through job satisfaction. This study uses quantitative analysis. The sample in this study consisted of 370 high school teachers in Medan City who came from schools with accreditation A. This sample was obtained from the results of filling out a questionnaire through the Googleform application. The data analysis used in this study is SEM-PLS. The results showed that directly the three variables namely competence, leadership style and job satisfaction had a significant effect on the performance of high school teachers in Medan City. It is also indicated that the competency and leadership style variables have a significant effect on the job satisfaction of high school teachers in Medan City. Furthermore, indirectly job satisfaction is able to mediate the effects of both competency and leadership style variables on the performance of high school teachers in Medan City.

Keyword: teacher performance, competence, leadership style, job satisfaction

1. INTRODUCTION

A strong nation and state must be built through educational development that prepares people to face and respond to existing challenges. Government efforts aimed at advancing the field of education are through passing laws and issuing regulations governing the administration of the national education system. Chapter 1 Article 1 Paragraph 1 of the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System defines: "Education is a conscious and planned effort to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students can develop their potential to have religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character, and the skills they need." As part of efforts to achieve national education goals, the government is making various efforts to expand learning opportunities, increase the relevance of education to the needs of the world of work, increase the effectiveness and efficiency of education, and improve the skills, competencies and qualifications of teachers and school principals.

Bangun (2016) explains that education is becoming more relevant both in terms of the number of graduates and the talent required for development. Efforts to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of education management are also carried out by managing, planning, and monitoring the implementation of education through education laws, curriculum, and the implementation of education both in the central and regional governments. The enactment of the Law on Education and the Law on Teachers and Lecturers is intended to lead to the

formation of state regulations, among other things, by the formation of the National Education Standards Agency.

School is a service-oriented educational institution with a vision, mission, goals and functions. Schools need professional employees, organizational work directed at school-based administration, and other financial and non-financial resources to achieve these visions, missions, goals and functions.

The schools as a whole consists of interconnected components that help students achieve their goals. Students, teachers, principals, teaching materials, curriculum, learning processes, environment, facilities, and outputs or results are among these components. All of these elements must work together to meet the needs of the times and changes in the social environment.

For this development to be effective, it must start with the issues that cause the school not to run as planned. This is reflected in efforts to introduce changes in the way of organization as well as the structure, process and system of the institution concerned so that it can better fulfill the vision and mission of the school institution concerned in accordance with the conception of institutional development (Bangun, 2012). As a result, any changes that occur in educational institutions must consider all components.

Changes to educational institutions (schools) must be carried out in accordance with the policies above them. The policy can be macro or micro management. Both in macro or micro management there should be an organic managerial function at the top of the organizational hierarchy. These functions include planning, organizing, directing, and controlling. All this must be done in order to achieve its main goal.

Table 1: Number of High School Teachers in Medan City

Academic Year	Public	Private	Total
2016/2017	1.353	2.444	3.797
2017/2018	1.350	2.657	4.007
2018/2019	1.360	2.658	4.018
2019/2020	1.290	2.808	4.098
2020/2021	1.398	3.090	4.488
2021/2022	1.381	3.464	4.845

Source: <https://dapo.dikdasmen.kemdikbud.go.id/sp/1/070000> (2021)

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND SUBMISSION OF HYPOTHESIS

2.1 Teacher Performance

According to Mangkunegara (2019: 31), the term performance comes from the word job performance or actual performance (work achievement or actual achievement achieved by a person), namely the work results in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties according to the responsibilities delegated to him. Furthermore, according to Tannady (2017: 154), performance is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by an

employee or a department or an organization in carrying out its tasks and targets according to the responsibilities assigned to it within a certain evaluation period. Employee performance is the result of implementing an organization's goals, therefore good performance is an important thing for all employees to do. Employee performance is the result in terms of quality and quantity that is achieved by an employee in carrying out tasks in accordance with assigned responsibilities (Mangkunegara, 2017:67). Furthermore, according to Bernadin and Russel (in Sapitri, 2016: 5), performance is a record of the outcomes resulting from the function of a particular job or activity during a certain period of time. There are dimensions and indicators of employee performance according to Sedarmayanti (2010: 263), namely:

1. Work performance, the indicators are work skills, potential for knowledge development through training, and completion of work in accordance with the time.
2. Expertise, the indicator is the ability of employees and educational background.
3. Behavior, the indicators are employee attitudes at work, employee loyalty, and relations with employees.

2.2 Competence

In general, competence can be understood as a combination of skills, personal attributes, and knowledge which is reflected through work behavior that can be observed, measured, and evaluated. Competence is divided into two types, namely soft competency or types of competencies that are closely related to the ability to manage work processes, human relations and build interactions with other people, and hard competencies or types of competencies related to functional or technical abilities of a job. Here are some definitions of competency according to some experts.

According to Spencer & Spencer (in Kandula, 2013), competency is an underlying characteristic of an individual related to a causal relationship of effective and/or superior implementation in a job or situation. George Klemp (in Edison et al, 2016) states that competency is a characteristic that underlies a person that produces effective work and/or superior performance.

Furthermore, according to Edison et al (2016) competence is an individual's ability to carry out a job correctly and have advantages based on matters relating to knowledge, skills, and attitudes.

Based on this definition, competence is an individual characteristic that includes knowledge, skills, and behaviors that produce effective work to achieve organizational goals.

2.3 Leadership

Leadership is the process of getting people to do their best to achieve the desired results. It can be described as the ability to convince others to behave differently. Leadership also involves developing and communicating a vision for the future.

According to Robbins & Coulter (2012) leadership is the process of influencing a group towards achieving goals. According to Armstong (2016), leadership is the process of getting

people to do their best to achieve the desired results. Another understanding according to Schermerhorn (2013) is that leadership is the process of inspiring others to work hard to complete important tasks.

Yuki in Gunawan (2015) says that leadership is a process to influence others to understand and agree with what needs to be done and how the task is done effectively, as well as a process to facilitate individual and group efforts to achieve common goals.

Based on some of the opinions of the experts that have been put forward, it can be defined that leadership is the behavior of an individual who leads an activity where the leader influences other people to be willing to work together to achieve organizational goals. The broad definition of leadership includes the process of influencing in determining organizational goals, motivating the behavior of followers to achieve goals, influencing the interpretation of the events of their followers, maintaining cooperative relationships and group work, gaining support and cooperation from people outside the group or organization.

From the definitions above, it can be seen that leadership is an important part of management, where a leader must be able to create harmonious integration with his subordinates. This also includes fostering cooperation, directing and encouraging the work passion of subordinates, influencing and shaping the attitudes and behavior of individuals and groups, thus forming the leadership style that leaders apply (Kamal, Winarso, and Sulistio, 2019).

2.4 Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction according to Edison et al (2016) is a set of employee feelings about things that are pleasant or not about a job they face. High job satisfaction is a characteristic of a well-managed organization and is basically the result of effective leadership. Job satisfaction will form a comfortable atmosphere and high morale. This is inseparable from the organizational culture in forming positive behavior and mutual respect, respecting one another, having a good work system, and openness, which behind it is managed by leaders/managers that are reliable and motivate and have good human relations. High job satisfaction is a characteristic of an organization that is managed professionally.

Job satisfaction is one of the most studied phenomena in human resource management and organizational behavior. It is often defined as “a pleasant or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's work or work experience” (Ćulibrk et al, 2018). The level of one's job satisfaction is an important component of the level of his work motivation which is a fundamental determinant of his behavior in an organization. So job satisfaction is the result of employees' perceptions of how well their work provides things that are considered important. Job satisfaction focuses on employees' attitudes toward their jobs and discussions of organizational commitment focus on employees' attitudes toward the organization as a whole.

According to Robbins and Judge (2015), job satisfaction is a positive feeling about work resulting from an evaluation of its characteristics. Someone with a high level of job satisfaction has positive feelings about his job, while someone with a low level has negative feelings. Job satisfaction theory (Wibowo, 2017) tries to reveal what makes people more satisfied with their

jobs. This theory also seeks a basis for the process of people's feelings towards job satisfaction. There are two theories of job satisfaction, namely two factors and value theory:

1) Two factor theory is a theory of job satisfaction which suggests that satisfaction and dissatisfaction are part of a different group of variables, namely motivators and hygiene factors. In this theory, dissatisfaction is associated with conditions around work such as working conditions, wages, security, quality of supervision, and relationships with other people. Instead of the work itself, because these factors prevent negative reactions, they are called hygiene or maintenance factors. Satisfaction is drawn from factors related to the job itself, such as the nature of the job, achievement on the job, promotion opportunities and opportunities for self-development, and recognition. Because these factors are related to high levels of job satisfaction, they are called motivators.

2) Value Theory, in this theory job satisfaction occurs at the level where the work results are received by the individual as expected. The more people who receive the results, the more satisfied the individual concerned will be, and vice versa. The key to satisfaction in this approach is the difference between the aspects of the job one has and one wants. The greater this difference, the lower one's satisfaction. This theory suggests that job satisfaction can be obtained from many factors; where an effective way to satisfy workers is to find what they want and if possible give it.

Figure 1: Relation between Variables

The hypotheses to be tested according to Figure 1 above are as follows:

1. Competence has a positive and significant effect on the job satisfaction of high school teachers in Medan City
2. Leadership style has a positive and significant effect on the job satisfaction of high school teachers in Medan City
3. Competence has a positive and significant effect on performance of high school teachers in Medan City

4. Leadership style has a positive and significant effect on performance of high school teachers in Medan City
5. Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on performance of high school teachers in Medan City
6. Competence has a positive and significant effect on performance through job satisfaction of high school teachers in Medan City
7. Leadership style has a positive and significant effect on performance through job satisfaction of high school teachers in Medan City

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This study uses quantitative analysis. The data were obtained from the results of filling out the questionnaire through the Googleform application which in this study were filled in by 370 high school teachers in Medan City who came from schools with accreditation A.

. Data were analyzed using a structural equation model (SEM) analysis based on partial least squares (PLS) which aims to examine the direct and indirect effects of the research variables used.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Measurement Model Analysis (Outer Model)

Figure 2: Results of Measurement Model Analysis

Figure 2 above shows that all variables have met the validity requirements with a loading factor value for all indicators > 0.7 . Thus the next test can be carried out.

Construct Reliability Test

Table 1: Results of Construct Reliability Analysis

Matrix	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extract...
	Cronbach...	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
X1	0.907	0.908	0.924	0.575
X2	0.906	0.907	0.923	0.571
Y	0.922	0.923	0.935	0.588
Z	0.920	0.921	0.933	0.583

The results of the analysis shown in Table 1 above show that the AVE value of each latent variable is > 0.5 and the composite reliability value and Cronbach's alpha value for each latent variable is greater than 0.7, so it can be concluded that the indicators of the variables are able to measure well.

Measurement Model Analysis (Inner Model)

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Table 2: Value of R-Square

Matrix	R Square	R Square Adjusted
	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Y	0.964	0.964
Z	0.947	0.947

Based on Table 2 above, it is known that the adjusted R-Square value for the teacher performance variable is 0.964 or 96.4% and the remaining 3.6% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study. For job satisfaction variable the R-Square adjusted value is 0.947 or 94.7% and the remaining 5.3% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

Predictive Relevance (Q²)

The value of Q² has the same meaning as the coefficient of determination R-Square. The value of Q-square (Q²) is greater than 0 indicating the model has predictive relevance. On the other

hand, the value of Q2 is less than 0 indicating that the model has less predictive relevance or in other words, if all the values of Q2 are higher, the model is considered to be more compatible with the data. Calculation of the value of Q2 can be done as follows.

$$Q2 = 1 - (1-R^2_1)(1-R^2_2)... (R_n^2)$$

$$Q2 = 1 - (1-0.964)(1-0.947)$$

$$Q2 = 1 - (0.036)(0.053)$$

$$Q2 = 0.998$$

Based on the results above, the value of Q2 is 0.998. So it can be concluded that all variables in this study, namely teacher performance, competence, leadership style, and job satisfaction contributed 99.8% of the original data in the structural model. Then the remaining 0.2% needs to be developed in addition to this research variable.

Effect Size (F2)

Effect size (F2) is determining the kindness of the model and also to find out whether the predictor variable has a weak, sufficient or strong effect at the structural level.

Hypothesis Test

Table 3: Direct Effects between Variables

	Original ...	Sample ...	Standard ...	T Statistic...	P Values
X1 -> Y	0.293	0.293	0.039	7.556	0.000
X1 -> Z	0.557	0.558	0.037	14.880	0.000
X2 -> Y	0.348	0.352	0.030	11.748	0.000
X2 -> Z	0.435	0.434	0.037	11.607	0.000
Z -> Y	0.360	0.355	0.042	8.644	0.000

1. The Effect of Competence Directly on Teacher Performance

Competence has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance. This result can be seen from the significance value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. This means that the more competence is increased, the performance of high school teachers in Medan City will significantly increase. The results of this study are in line with the studies of Arifah, 2018; Arlita et al., 2020; Chandra et al., 2021; Fachmi et al., 2021; Kanya et al., 2021; Kesumawati & Kristiawan, 2018; Maritasari et al., 2020; May et al., 2020; Muhammad Arifin, 2015; Murkatik et al., 2020a, 2020b; Nurhasni et al., 2020; Owan & Agunwa, 2019; Poro et al., 2018; Rahmatullah, 2016; Sinaga et al., 2021; Singerin, 2021; Siri et al., 2020; Wahyudin, 2016; Warner, 2019; Yusnita et al., 2018; and Zubaidah et al., 2021 showed that there is a positive

effect of teacher competence on the performance of teachers, where high competence tends to produce high performance, and conversely teachers with poor competence tend to show poor performance. A person's performance is based on understanding the knowledge, skills, expertise and behavior required to do a good job. Mulyasa argued that teachers who have high performance will be passionate and try to improve their competence in relation to planning, implementation, and assessment so that optimal results are obtained.

2. The Effect of Leadership Style Directly on Teacher Performance

It is known that the significance value of leadership style is 0.000, which is less than 0.05. This means that the more the leadership style increases, the performance of high school teachers in Medan City will significantly increase. This result is consistent with the results of studies conducted by Abu Nasra & Arar (2020); Andriani et al. (2018); Dian et al. (2021); Handayani et al. (2021); Hartiwi et al. (2020); Herman et al. (2021); Juwaini et al. (2021); Maheshwari (2022); Melianah et al. (2021); Mulyani et al. (2020); Natsir et al. (2020); Nurabadi et al. (2021); Prasetyo (2021); Pristiyowati et al. (2021); Rahayu et al. (2019); Saleem et al. (2020); Siahaan et al. (2020); Sukarni et al. (2021); Sukmawati et al. (2019); Susilawati (2021); Wahab et al. (2020); and Yulyanti & Hasanah (2021) which also shows that good leadership will support high teacher performance.

3. The Effect of Job Satisfaction Directly on Teacher Performance

Job satisfaction has a direct and significant positive effect on teacher performance, where these results can be seen from a significance value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05. This means that the higher the job satisfaction, the higher the performance of high school teachers in Medan City. The results of this study are in line with study conducted by Ayu Desi Indrawati (2013) and also in line with studies conducted by Wanda Febriyana (2015), Ginta Vonlihana Putri NCP Paparang (2021), Iwan Kurnia Wijaya (2018), and T.F. Lie (2018).

4. The Effect of Competence Directly on Job Satisfaction

Competence has a significant effect on the job satisfaction of high school teachers in Medan City. This can be seen from the significance value of the competency variable of 0.000 which is less than 0.05. This means that increasing competency will affect teacher performance, that is, if competence increases, teacher performance will also increase accordingly. These results are consistent with the results of a study conducted by Mutmainah Isnaini (2015), and with a study conducted by A. Samad, M. Yusuf Vol. 4, No 8 (2015): JURNAL KEBANGSAAN, and with a study published in the JOURNAL OF ECONOMICS AND MANAGEMENT, as well as the study conducted by A. Samad, M. Yusuf (2015). But these results contradict a study conducted by Anggi Meidita Vol. 2, No 2 (2019) in a scientific journal of Masters in Management.

5. The Effect of Leadership Style Directly on Job Satisfaction

It is known that the significance value of the leadership style variable is 0.000 which is smaller than 0.05. This means that the more the leadership style increases, the job satisfaction of high school teachers in Medan City will significantly increase. These results are consistent with the

results of studies conducted by Andri et al. and Made Suprpta et.al (2015) which shows that leadership has a significant positive effect on job satisfaction. Similar results were also found in a study conducted by Wehelmina Rumawas and a study conducted by AY Pratama (2022).

Table 4: Indirect Effects between Variables

	Original ...	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviat...	T Statistic...	P Values
X1 -> Z -> Y	0.200	0.196	0.025	8.075	0.000
X2 -> Z -> Y	0.156	0.153	0.028	5.610	0.000

6. The Effect of Competence Indirectly on Teacher Performance through Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction significantly mediates the effect of competence on the performance of high school teachers in Medan City. This can be seen from the significance value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05. The results of this study are in accordance with the results of studies conducted by Hartiwi (2015); Raharjaya & Kepramareni (2020); Abbas et al. (2019); Abdullah La Tunrung et al. (2019); Djou & Lukiastuti (2021); Fajrian et al. (2020); Hartiwi (2015); Jusmin et al. (2016); Kiwan & Heryanto (2020); Magnano et al. (2020); Marwah Aya Shofia (2021); Mouratidis et al. (2008); Nasir et al. (2017); Nugraha et al. (2022); Sabuhari et al. (2020); Shofia (2020); Sun (2016); and Tunrung et al. (2019), the difference is only in the research object where these studies were carried out in a social environment that was not specified in the school environment of the teachers.

7. The Effect of Leadership Style Indirectly on Teacher Performance through Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction can significantly mediate the effect of leadership style on the performance of high school teachers in Medan City. This can be seen from the significance value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05. The results of this study are in accordance with the results of studies conducted by Suartini et al., (2020) and Sulistiyowati (2015) which show that job satisfaction can mediate the effect of leadership style on performance. Similar results were also found in the studies of Edward (2020), Nugroho et al (2021), and Mansyur et al (2017) which stated that performance fully mediates the relationship between leadership style and performance.

V. CONCLUSION

The conclusion that can be made in this study is that the three variables namely competence, leadership style, and job satisfaction directly have a significant effect on performance and competence and leadership style have a significant effect on job satisfaction of high school teachers in Medan City. In addition, job satisfaction can indirectly mediate the effect of competence and leadership style on the performance of high school teachers in Medan City.

References

- Abbas, M., Raja, U., Anjum, M., & Bouckenooghe, D. (2019). Perceived competence and impression management: Testing the mediating and moderating mechanisms. *International Journal of Psychology*, 54(5). <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijop.12515>
- Abdullah La Tunrung, H. H., Umar, F., & Sumardi, S. (2019). The Effect of Competence, Organisational Culture, and Organisational Commitment on Job Satisfaction and Its Impact on Employee Performance at PT. Haji La Tunrung A.M.C in Makassar. *Hasanuddin Journal Of Business Strategy*, 1(2). <https://doi.org/10.26487/Hjbs.V1i2.222>
- Abu Nasra, M., & Arar, K. (2020). Leadership Style And Teacher Performance: Mediating Role Of Occupational Perception. *International Journal Of Educational Management*, 34(1). <https://doi.org/10.1108/Ijem-04-2019-0146>
- Abdullah, M. (2014). *Manajemen dan Evaluasi Kinerja Karyawan*. Penerbit Aswaja Pressindo, Yogyakarta.
- Adripen, Rafli, D., & Amra, A. (2021). Pengaruh Pelaksanaan Supervisi Akademik Kepala Sekolah dan Gaya Kepemimpinan Terhadap Kinerja Guru. *Al-Ikhtibar: Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan*, 8(2). <https://doi.org/10.32505/ikhtibar.v8i2.628>
- Afsar, B., Masood, M., & Umrani, W. A. (2019). The role of job crafting and knowledge sharing on the effect of transformational leadership on innovative work behavior. *Personnel Review*, 48(5), 1186–1208. <https://doi.org/10.1108/PR-04-2018-0133>
- Azulaidin, A., & Rosmika, E. (2021). Pengaruh Kompetensi Guru, Motivasi Dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Guru. *Juripol*, 4(2). <https://doi.org/10.33395/juripol.v4i2.11119>
- Bayu, K. (2017). Kepuasan Kerja Memoderasi Pengaruh Lingkungan Kerja Dan Kepemimpinan Kepala Sekolah Terhadap Kinerja Guru Smk Negeri 1 Pati. *Bima Bingkai Manajemen*, 1(20).
- Benton, J. E., Swami, P., & Instruction, W. C. For C. And. (2007). *Creating Cultures Of Peace: Pedagogical Thought And Practice. Selected Papers From The 10th Triennial World Conference (September 10-15, 2001, Madrid, Spain)*. In World Council For Curriculum And Instruction.
- Birks, D. F. (2016). *Marketing research*. In *The Marketing Book: Seventh Edition*.
- Bhutta, Zahra Masood; Hussain, Khadim; and Zhao, Minjua. (2018). Job Crafting Practices and Work Satisfaction: Evidence from Higher Education Sector in Shaanxi, China. *The Educational Review*. DOI: 15804/tner.2018.52.2.05.
- Bua, P. T., Kristianto, T., & Daengs Gs, A. (2020a). The Impact Of Work Environment, Communication And Leadership On Performance Of Employees In Tarakan City Education Office. *Jmm17: Jurnal Ilmu Ekonomi Dan Manajemen*, 7(01). <https://doi.org/10.30996/Jmm.V7i01.3544>
- Bua, P. T., Kristianto, T., & Daengs Gs, A. (2020b). The Impact Of Work Environment, Communication And Leadership On Performance Of Employees In Tarakan City Education Office. *Jmm17*, 7(01). <https://doi.org/10.30996/Jmm17.V7i01.3544>
- Chandra, J. A., G, N. N. P. M., & Qomariah, N. (2021). Impact Of Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Leadership, Individual Characteristics And Competence On Teacher Performance. *Jurnal Manajemen Dan Bisnis Indonesia*, 6(2). <https://doi.org/10.32528/Jmbi.V6i2.4091>
- Chang, Sujin; Han, Kihye and Cho, Yongae. (2020). Association of Happiness and NursingWork Environments with Job Crafting among Hospital Nurses in South Korea. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 2020, 17.

- Civelek, Mustafa Emre. (2018). Essentials of Structural Equation Modeling. In Zea Books. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13014/K2SJ1HR5>
- Čulibrk, J., Delić, M., Mitrović, S., & Čulibrk, D. (2018). Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment and Job Involvement: The Mediating Role of Job Involvement. *Frontiers in psychology*, 9, 132. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.00132>
- Dan, C. I., Roşca, A. C., & Mateizer, A. (2020). Job Crafting and Performance in Firefighters: The Role of Work Meaning and Work Engagement. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11(May), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00894>.
- Dian, D., Suhendar, R., & Sovian, S. (2021). The Influence Of Principal's Leadership On Teacher Performance. *Al-Ishlah: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 13(3). <https://doi.org/10.35445/Alishlah.V13i3.697>
- Djou, L. D. G., & Lukiastuti, F. (2021). The Influence Of Competence And Locus Of Control On Government Internal Auditor Performance: The Role Of Job Satisfaction. *Quality - Access To Success*, 22(182).
- Edison, Emron; Anwar, Yohny dan Imas Komariyah, Imas, (2016). *Manajemen Sumber Daya. Manusia*. Alfabeta, Bandung.
- Edward, Yusuf Ronny dan Kaban, Lila Maria. (2020). The Effect of Transformational Leadership and Competence on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as Intervening Variable. *Academic Journal of Economic Studies*. Vol. 6, No. 2, June 2020, pp. 62–72. ISSN 2393-4913, ISSN On-line 2457-5836
- Eliza, M., & Pratiwi, N. A. (2021). Implications Of Organizational Culture, Servant Leadership, Competence On Quality Of Work Life And Employee Performance Syar'i Garment. *Laa Maisyir : Jurnal Ekonomi Islam*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.24252/Lamaisyir.V8i1.18674>
- Elsayed, Reda Shehata. (2019). Nurses' Job Crafting and its' relationship with their Job Demands, Job Resources, and Career Competencies. *International Journal of Novel Research in Healthcare and Nursing* Vol. 6, Issue 2, pp: (1459-1474).
- Engkoswara (1987). *Dasar-dasar Administrasi Pendidikan. Proyek Pengembangan Lembaga Pendidikan Tenaga Kependidikan*, Depdikbud, Jakarta.
- Fachmi, M., Mustafa, M., & Ngandoh, A. M. (2021). The Role Of Motivation And Professional Competence In Improving Teacher Performance. *Journal Of Digital Learning And Education*, 1(01). <https://doi.org/10.52562/Jdle.V1i01.14>
- Fajrian, A., Musnadi, S., & Nadirsyah. (2020). The Effect Of Competence, Professionalism And Work Environment On Job Satisfaction And Its Impact On Internal Auditor Performance Of Pt Bank Negara Indonesia. *International Journal Of Business Management And Economic Review*, 03(04). <https://doi.org/10.35409/Ijbmer.2020.3190>
- Handayani, T., Fitria, H., & Puspita, Y. (2021). The Influence Of Organization Atmosphere And School Leadership On Teacher Performance In Senior High School. *Jpgi (Jurnal Penelitian Guru Indonesia)*, 6(2). <https://doi.org/10.29210/021067jpgi0005>
- Harahap, V. A., & Hidayat, W. (2016a). Pengaruh Motivasi Dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Melalui Kepuasan Kerja Sebagai Variabel Intervening. *Jurnal Ilmu Administrasi Bisnis*, 5(3).
- Harahap, V. A., & Hidayat, W. (2016b). Pengaruh Motivasi Dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Melalui Kepuasan Kerja Sebagai Variabel Intervening (Studi Pada Pt. Taspen (Persero) Kantor Cabang Utama Semarang). *Jurnal Ilmu Administrasi Bisnis*, 5(3).

- Hari, Lin; Mardi, Nugroho dan Hartati, C. Sri. (2021). Pengaruh Komitmen, Komunikasi dan Kompetensi Terhadap Kinerja Guru Melalui Motivasi Kerja Guru SMK Negeri Dander Kabupaten Bojonegoro. *Jurnal Mitra Pendidikan (JMP) Online* Vol. 5 No. 2 Februari (2021) 126-141.
- Haroon, M., & Akbar, A. (2016). Leader's Motivating Language And Job Performance: Mediating Role Of Job Satisfaction. *Numl International Journal Of Business & Management*, 11(1).
- Hartina, Sitti; Suharso, Putut; Umam, Rofiqul; Syazali, Muhamad; Lestari, Bella Dwi; Roslina and Jermisittiparsert, Kittisak. (2019). Teacher's Performance Management: The Role of Principal's Leadership, Work Environment and Motivation in Tegal City, Indonesia. *Management Science Letters* • July 2019.
- Hartini, H.-, Rahmawati, R., & Asmin, E. A. (2021). Motivasi, Komitmen Organisasi, Kompetensi dan Dampaknya Terhadap Kinerja Guru. *Jurnal Manajemen*, 12(1). <https://doi.org/10.32832/jm-uika.v12i1.3950>
- Hartiwi. (2015). Analisis Pengaruh Karakteristik Pekerjaan Dan Kompetensi Terhadap Kinerja Guru Dengan Mediasi Kepuasan Kerja (Studi Pada Smp Muhammadiyah Se Kabupaten Pati). *Jurnal Mahasiswa Pasca Sarjana*, 1(1).
- Hartiwi, H., Kozlova, A. Y., & Masitoh, F. (2020). The Effect Of Certified Teacher And Principal Leadership Toward Teachers' Performance. *International Journal Of Educational Review*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.33369/Ijer.V2i1.10629>
- Haryanto, A. T., & Dewi, S. N. (2020). Peran Kepemimpinan Efektif dan Kedisiplinan Terhadap Komitmen Organisasi dan Motivasi Maslow Pada Kinerja Tugas Guru di Sekolah Dasar. *Jurnal Basicedu*, 4(4). <https://doi.org/10.31004/basicedu.v4i4.448>
- Ideswal, I., Yahya, Y., & Alkadri, H. (2020). Kontribusi Iklim Sekolah dan Kepemimpinan Kepala Sekolah terhadap Kinerja Guru Sekolah Dasar. *Jurnal Basicedu*, 4(2). <https://doi.org/10.31004/basicedu.v4i2.381>
- Ilham, I., & Yaakob, D. (2014). Teacher's Job Satisfaction As A Mediator Of The Relationship Between Ethical Leadership And Organizational Commitment In School. *International Journal Of Scientific Research And Education*, 2(8).
- Imbron, I., Paeno, P., & Ratnasih, P. (2021). Pengaruh Disiplin Kerja Dan Kompetensi Terhadap Kinerja Guru Pada SMK Negeri 2 Di Kota Tangerang Selatan. *Jurnal Ilmiah PERKUSI*, 1(2). <https://doi.org/10.32493/j.perkusi.v1i2.11035>
- Immah, F., Sukidin, S., & Kartini, T. (2020). Pengaruh Kompetensi Profesional Guru Terhadap Kinerja Guru Di Sma Negeri 01 Kalisat Tahun Pelajaran 2018/2019. *Jurnal Pendidikan Ekonomi: Jurnal Ilmiah Ilmu Pendidikan, Ilmu Ekonomi Dan Ilmu Sosial*, 14(1). <https://doi.org/10.19184/jpe.v14i1.12493>
- Iskandar. (2017a). Pengaruh Karakteristik Individu, Beban Kerja Dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Pada Kantor Inspektorat Daerah Provinsi Sulawesi Tengah. *Katalogis*, 5(1).
- Iskandar. (2017b). Pengaruh Karakteristik Individu, Beban Kerja Dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Pada Kantor Pelayanan Pajak
- Pembangunan UIN Jakarta Tingkat Ibtidaiyah, Tsanawiyah, dan Aliyah) Skripsi. Fakultas Ekonomi Dan Bisnis, 1(January).
- Ivan Fanani Qomusuddin, & Ubun Bunyamin. (2020). Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Kepala Sekolah dan Kompetensi Guru Terhadap Kinerja Guru. *Jurnal Pendidikan Indonesia*, 1(2). <https://doi.org/10.36418/japendi.v1i2.3>
- Iwan Hermawan, Et. Al. (2020). Job Identity Satisfaction As A Concept Of Mediation For Change Leadership To Support Change Commitment: A Perspective Of Human Capital Theory. *International Journal Of Advanced Science And Technology*, 29(2 Se-Articles).

- Jajang, J., Supriyanto, S., & Putra, D. E. (2021). Analisis Faktor-Faktor Yang Berpengaruh Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Pt. Kereta Api Indonesia (Persero) Daop 5 Purwokerto Dengan Partial Least Square. *Jurnal Ilmiah Matematika Dan Pendidikan Matematika*, 12(2). <https://doi.org/10.20884/1.Jmp.2020.12.2.3613>
- Jaliah, J., Fitria, H., & Martha, A. (2020). Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Kepala Sekolah dan Manajemen Kepala Sekolah terhadap Kinerja Guru. *Journal of Education Research*, 1(2). <https://doi.org/10.37985/joe.v1i2.14>
- Jalil, A. (2020). Pengaruh Beban Kerja, Stres Kerja dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Guru Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 2 Kota Palu. *Jurnal Ilmu Perbankan Dan Keuangan Syariah*, 1(2). <https://doi.org/10.24239/jipsya.v1i2.14.117-134>
- Juniarti, E., Ahyani, N., & Ardiansyah, A. (2020). Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Kepala Sekolah dan Disiplin Guru terhadap Kinerja Guru. *Journal of Education Research*, 1(3). <https://doi.org/10.37985/joe.v1i3.21>
- Jusmin, A., Said, S., Jobhaar Bima, M., & Alam, R. (2016). Specific Determinants Of Work Motivation, Competence, Organizational Climate, Job Satisfaction And Individual Performance: A Study Among Lecturers. *Journal Of Business And Management Sciences*, 4(3).
- Juwaini, A., Fahlevi, M., Nadeak, M., Novitasari, D., Nagoya, R., Surya Wanasida, A., & Purwanto, A. (2021). The Role Of Work Motivation, Organizational Culture And Leadership On Job Satisfaction And Teachers Performance : An Empirical Study On Indonesian Senior High Schools. *Turkish Journal Of Computer And Mathematics Education*, 12(12).
- Ibanez, Onintze Letona; Rodriguez, Silvia Martinez; Marques, Nuria Ortiz; Carrasco, Maria, and Amillano, Alejandro. (2021). Job Crafting and Work Engagement: The Mediating Role of Work Meaning. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health (IJERPH)*, Volume 18, Issue 10.
- Kustanto, H., Muazza, M., & Haryanto, E. (2021). Pengaruh Gaya Kepemimpinan, Motivasi dan Disiplin Kerja terhadap Kinerja Guru. *EDUKATIF: JURNAL ILMU PENDIDIKAN*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.31004/edukatif.v4i1.1742>
- Lee, Jae Young and Lee, Yunsoo. (2018). Crafting and Performance: Literature Review and Implications for Human Resource Development. *Human Resource Development Review* 00(0).
- Lee, K. Y., & Song, J. S. (2021). The Effect of Empowering Leadership on Intrinsic Motivation, Job Crafting and Job Performance. *The Journal of the Korea Contents Association*, 21(3), 463-477.
- Lichtenthaler, Philipp Wolfgang and Fischbach, Andrea. (2018). Leadership, Job Crafting, and Employee Health and Performance", *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, <https://doi.org/10.1108/>
- Lubis, R. P., Pasaribu, F., & Tufty, Z. (2020). Pengaruh Kompetensi, Motivasi Kerja dan Lingkungan Terhadap Kinerja Guru SMA Negeri 15 Medan. *Jurnal AKMAMI (Akuntansi, Manajemen, Ekonomi)*, 2(2).
- Lumintang, Saskia dan Rufial. (2021). Pengaruh Kompetensi, Kepemimpinan, dan Lingkungan Kerja terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Direktorat Pelayanan Kantor Pusat BPJS Ketenagakerjaan. <https://journals.upi-yai.ac.id/index.php/IKRAITHEKONOMIKA/article/download/1683/1386/>
- Lustriningsih, L. (2021). Pengaruh Motivasi terhadap Kinerja Guru Dimoderasi Gaya Kepemimpinan Transformasional dan Budaya Organisasional. *Jiip - Jurnal Ilmiah Ilmu Pendidikan*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.54371/jiip.v4i1.202>
- Lutfiyanto, Rizky Pradana; Huda, Nurul dan Hulmansyah. (2020). Pengaruh Pengembangan Karir dan Gaya Kepemimpinan Terhadap Kinerja Guru dengan Organizational Citizenhsip Behavior sebagai Variable Mediasi (Study Pada Guru Sekolah Menengah Kejuruan). *Journal of Economics and Business Aseanomics* 5(2) 2020.

- M Yusrin Njib. (2020). Pengaruh Beban Kerja Dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karayawan Dimediasi Oleh Kepuasan Kerja Pada Umkm Maju Makmur Pandaan Pasuruan. In Central Library Of Maulana Malik Ibrahim State Islamic University Of Malang.
- Madrid, E. N. M., Berowa, A. E., & Vosotros, A. A. (2019). Evaluation of teachers' performance at the college of social sciences and humanities, mindanao state university, main campus using formal concept analysis. *Journal of Education Khon Kaen University (Graduate Studies Research)*, 13(1), 61-74.
- Magnano, P., Lodi, E., & Boerchi, D. (2020). The Role Of Non-Intellective Competences And Performance In College Satisfaction. *Interchange*, 51(3). <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10780-019-09385-X>
- Masoko, F. F., Katuuk, D. A., Rotty, V. N. J., & Lengkong, J. S. J. (2021). Pengaruh Perilaku Kepemimpinan dan Kompensasi terhadap Kinerja Guru SMP Advent di Minahasa Utara. *Jurnal Bahana Manajemen Pendidikan*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.24036/jbmp.v10i1.112135>
- Massoudi, Aram & Hamdi, Sameer. (2017). The Consequence of work environment on Employees Productivity. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*. 19. 35-42. <http://doi.10.9790/487X-1901033542>
- May, L. F., Abdurrahman, A., Hariri, H., Sowiyah, S., & Rahman, B. (2020). The Influence Of Principal Managerial Competence On Teacher Performance At Schools In Bandar Lampung. *Tadris: Jurnal Keguruan Dan Ilmu Tarbiyah*, 5(1). <https://doi.org/10.24042/Tadris.V5i1.5391>
- Megiati, Y. E., & Pratiwi, N. K. (2021). Persepsi Guru atas Supervisi Kepemimpinan Kepala Madrasah terhadap Kinerja Guru. *SAP (Susunan Artikel Pendidikan)*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.30998/sap.v6i1.9357>
- Melianah, A., Matin, M., & Santosa, H. (2021). The Influence Of Transformational Leadership And Interpersonal Communication On Teachers' Performance. *Al-Ishlah: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 13(1). <https://doi.org/10.35445/Alishlah.V13i1.574>
- Meidiana, M., Ahmad, S., & Destiniar, D. (2020). Pengaruh Kompetensi Manajerial Kepala Sekolah Dan Supervisi Akademik Terhadap Kinerja Guru. *Jmksp (Jurnal Manajemen, Kepemimpinan, Dan Supervisi Pendidikan)*, 5(2). <https://doi.org/10.31851/jmksp.v5i2.3754>
- Miraglia, M., Cenciotti, R., Alessandri, G., & Borgogni, L. (2017). Translating self-efficacy in job performance over time: The role of job crafting. *Human Performance*, 30(5), 254–271. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08959285.2017.1373115>
- Moon, Tae-Won; Youn, Nara; Hur, Won-Moo; and Kim, Kyeong-Mi, (2018). Does Employees' Spirituality Enhance Job Performance? The Mediating Roles of Intrinsic Motivation and Job Crafting. Springer Science+Business Media, LLC, part of Springer Nature.
- Mouratidis, A., Vansteenkiste, M., Lens, W., & Sideridis, G. (2008). The Motivating Role Of Positive Feedback In Sport And Physical Education: Evidence For A Motivational Model. *Journal Of Sport And Exercise Psychology*, 30(2). <https://doi.org/10.1123/Jsep.30.2.240>
- Muhammad Arifin, H. (2015). The Influence Of Competence, Motivation, And Organisational Culture To High School Teacher Job Satisfaction And Performance. *International Education Studies*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.5539/Ies.V8n1p38>
- Mukhtar, Jazuli. (2018). Pengaruh Lingkungan Kerja dan Motivasi Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Guru pada Pondok Pesantren Asshiddiqiyah Jakarta. *Jurnal Disrupsi Bisnis*, Vol. 1, No.3, November 2018.
- Muslimin, S. (2019). Pengaruh Lingkungan Kerja Dan Penempatan Home Base Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Serta Implikasinya Pada Kinerja Account Representative Kantor Pelayanan Pajak Pratama Surabaya Area Jagir Wonokromo. *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen*, 5(3).

- Narasuci, W., Setiawan, M., & N. (2018). Effect of Work Environment on Lecturer Performance Mediated by Work Motivation and Job Satisfaction. *Journal of Applied Management*, 16(4), 645–653. <http://dx.doi.org/10.21776/ub.jam.2018.016.04.11>
- Narayanamma, P. L. (2017). A Study On Impact Of Balance Scorecard Implementation On Job Satisfaction Of Employees In Selescted Public And Privete Sectoc. *Shanlax International Journal Of Arts, Science And Humanities*, 4(3).
- Nasir, M. J. A., Wiyono, B. B., Supriyono, ., & Supriyanto, A. (2017). The Relationship Between Motivation, Organisational Commitment And Competence With Job Satisfaction And Lecturers Performance. *International Journal Of Learning And Development*, 7(3). <https://doi.org/10.5296/Ijld.V7i3.11688>
- Natsir, U. D., Tangkeallo, D. I., & Tangdialla, R. (2020). Effect Of Principal’s Leadership On Teacher Performance In Junior High School: A Case Of Indonesia. *International Journal Of Scientific And Technology Research*, 9(2).
- Nguyen, Ha Minh; Nguyen, Cuong; Ngo. Trung Thanh, and Nguyen, Luan Vinh. (2019). The Effect of Job Crafting in on Work Enggagement and Work Performance: A Study of Vietnamese Commercial Banks. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business Vol 6 No 2 (2019) 189-201.*
- Ningrum, Komang Septia Cahya. (2016). Pengaruh Kompetensi Guru Terhadap Kinerja Guru SMP Negeri 6 Singaraja. *Jurnal Program Studi Pendidikan Ekonomi (JPPE)*. Volume: 7 Nomor: 2 Tahun: 2016.
- Novitasari, D., Asbari, M., Wijayanti, L. M., Hyun, C. C., & Farhan, M. (2020). The Role Of Religiosity, Leadership Style, Job Satisfaction And Organizational Citizenship Behavior Mediation On Woman Teachers’ Performance. *Solid State Technology*, 63(6).
- Nuraeni, N. A., Affandi, I., & Heryani, A. (2020). Pengaruh Implementasi Kebijakan Sertifikasi Guru, Kompetensi Guru Terhadap Kinerja Guru Di Mts Al-Muqowamah Singaparna Tasikmalaya. *Naturalistic : Jurnal Kajian Penelitian Pendidikan Dan Pembelajaran*, 4(2a). <https://doi.org/10.35568/naturalistic.v4i2a.810>
- Nurdianti, Raden Roro Suci. (2017). Pengaruh Kompetensi Profesional Dan Kompetensi Pedagogik Terhadap Kinerja Guru Ekonomi SMA Negeri Di Kota Bandung. *Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen & Bisnis Vol. 18 No. 2, 2017.*
- Pratiwis, E. R., & Yuniantos, A. (2018). Kepuasan Kerja Sebagai Mediasi Pengaruh Motivasi, Lingkungan Kerja, Terpersepsi Terhadap Kinerja. *Prosiding Sendi_U: Universitas Stikubank Semarang*, 4.
- Pristyowati, D., Rahayu, S., Wahidmurni, W., & Supriyanto, A. S. (2021). The Education Function Of Effectiveness On Leadership Behavior, School Climate, And Teacher Performance. *Manageria: Jurnal Manajemen Pendidikan Islam*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.14421/Manageria.2021.61.03>
- Prihanto, Dwi Agung. (2017). Pengaruh Lingkungan Kerja dan Motivasi Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Guru Militer di Pusat Pendidikan Infanteri. *Jurnal Program Studi Strategi Pertahanan Darat*, April 2017, Volume 3, Nomor 1.
- Purwanto, E., & Solichin, M. R. (2020). Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Transformasional, Lingkungan Kerja Fisik, dan Disiplin Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Guru(Studi Kasus Pada Guru PNS di MTS N 5 Kebumen). *Jurnal Ilmiah Mahasiswa Manajemen, Bisnis Dan Akuntansi (JIMMBA)*, 2(6).
- Rachmawati, T., & Daryanto. (2013). *Penilaian Kinerja Profesi Guru dan Angka Kreditnya (Edisi Pert)*. Gava Media.
- Raharjaya, I., & Kepramareni, P. (2020). Influence Of Motivation Of Work And Competence On Performance Of Teacher With Job Satisfaction As Variable Mediation At Smk Ti Bali Global Denpasar. *Research*, 11(02).

- Rahayu, B., Idris, F., & Herawati, T. (2019). Effect Of Principal's Transformational Leadership Style On Teacher Performance. *International Journal For Educational And Vocational Studies*, 1(5). <https://doi.org/10.29103/Ijevs.V1i5.1614>
- Rahmania, N D Agustin, S. (2020). Pengaruh Kepemimpinan, Disiplin Kerja, Motivasi, Dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Guru Smk Dr. Soetomo Surabaya. *Jurnal Ilmu Dan Riset Manajemen*, 3(12).
- Rahmatullah, M. (2016). The Relationship Between Learning Effectiveness, Teacher Competence And Teachers Performance Madrasah Tsanawiyah At Serang, Banten, Indonesia. *Higher Education Studies*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.5539/Hes.V6n1p169>
- Rakhmawan, M. (2016). Pengaruh Budaya Kerja Dan Lingkungan Kerja Fisik Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan (Studi Pada Karyawan Pt. Semen Indonesia (Persero) Tbk). *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis S1 Universitas Brawijaya*, 35(2).
- Susilowati, Yunita Henny; Sudrajat, Ajat dan Padillah, Ella. (2021). Pengaruh Kompetensi dan Supervisi Akademik terhadap Kinerja Guru SDN di Kecamatan Pamulang. *Jurnal Studi Guru dan Pembelajaran*, Vol. 4, No. 2, Mei - Agustus 2021.
- Svicher, A., & Di Fabio, A. (2021). Job Crafting: A Challenge to Promote Decent Work for Vulnerable Workers. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12.
- Thakkar, J. J. (2020). *Structural Equation Modelling: Application for Research and Practice (with AMOS and R)*. Jerman: Springer Nature Singapore.
- Thahir, M. (2020). Pengaruh Lingkungan Kerja Fisik Dan Non-Fisik Terhadap Kinerja Guru. *Jurnal Ilmiah Islamic Resources*, 16(2). <https://doi.org/10.33096/jiir.v16i2.12>
- The Effect Of Transformational Leadership And Work Motivation On Teacher Performance Through Teacher Discipline. (2019). *Journal Of K6, Education, And Management*, 2(4). <https://doi.org/10.11594/Jk6em.02.04.09>
- Yusnita, Y., Eriyanti, F., Engkizar, E., Anwar, F., Putri, N. E., Arifin, Z., & Syafril, S. (2018). The Effect Of Professional Education And Training For Teachers (Plpg) In Improving Pedagogic Competence And Teacher Performance. *Tadris: Jurnal Keguruan Dan Ilmu Tarbiyah*, 3(2). <https://doi.org/10.24042/Tadris.V3i2.2701>
- Yusuf, R. H., Mas'ud, M., & Daud, A. (2020). Analisis Pengaruh Kualitas Lingkungan Kerja Dan Motivasi Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Dengan Kepuasan Kerja Sebagai Variabel Mediasi Pada Badan Kepegawaian Pendidikan Dan Pelatihan Daerah Kab. Kepulauan Selayar. *Nobel Mangement Review*, 1(2).
- Zhang, Chunyu and Liu, Liping. (2020). The effect of job crafting to job performance. *Journal of Knowledge Management research and Practice*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14778238.2020.1762517>
- Zubaidah, R. A., Haryono, S., & Udin, U. (2021). The Effects Of Principal Leadership And Teacher Competence On Teacher Performance: The Role Of Work Motivation. *Quality - Access To Success*, 22(180).
- Zulfardiansyah, Ratnawati, V., & Basri, Y. M. (2016). Pengaruh Profesionalisme, Gaya Kepemimpinan, Lingkungan Kerja Dan Kecerdasan Emosional Terhadap Kinerja Pengelola Keuangan Pada Satuan Kerja Perangkat Daerah (Skpd) Kabupaten Indragiri Hilir. *Jom Fekon*, 1(2).